

FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE-PRAGMATIC DIRECTION

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Abstract

This article is devoted to summarizing the achievements of pragmalinguistics, which is a relatively new branch of linguistics, and to the scientific analysis of theoretical views about its prospects. The article examines the initial experiments, which gathered a wide range of scientific materials on the essence and practical importance of ethnopragmatics, sociopragmatics, comparative pragmatics and other scientific directions, which are the "descendants" of pragmalinguistics.

Keywords

Linguistics, pragmatics, ethnopragmatics, sociopragmatics, pragmalinguistics, concept, phenomena, psychosystematic, speech phenomena, diachrony, internal, linguistic, voluntary, conditional.

I. INTRODUCTION

The formation and development of any field of science begins with the emergence of interest in the object of this field. Curiosity begets questions. Linguistics is no exception. The emergence and development of this science is nothing more than the search for answers to questions related to the language system, the construction of linguistic units, their composition, and their use in everyday life and social activities. But in linguistics, as in other subjects, it is an important condition that the selection of questions is directed to a scientific goal, and that the answers to them correspond to reality. Otherwise, if it is completely impossible to find an answer to the question, or if the question is formulated too abstractly, it is not a question that such an exercise will turn into a question-and-answer game consisting of empty thoughts and "fudging" statements.

Of course, it is not easy to avoid this danger, to avoid "dry talk" - speculative philosophy. For just one example, linguists, philosophers, theologians, etc., for more than 2000 years, have been eager to find the most mature language, which fully and accurately reflects reality, without any flaws in terms of lexical and grammatical system, and which is convenient for use in written and oral communication. In the Middle Ages, there was a prevailing opinion that such a mature language existed at the time, and if the means of communication in the Garden of Eram were

restored, humanity would have the ability to perceive and express reality truthfully, and any misunderstandings and conflicts between people and nations would be easily eliminated. We are also far from calling the discussion of the "mature language" problem a completely ineffective exercise.

Because, firstly, any science requires its object to be complete and accurate, and secondly, a negative result for scientific research is also the result of an experiment necessary for the proof of a scientific hypothesis. After all, this problem probably did not occupy the minds of many leaders of science in the West and the East for nothing, German scientist Arno Borst to create a seven-volume treatise (Borst 1957-63), the French linguist Marie-Lucy Demonit completes 700 pages (Demonit 1992), Italian semiotician Umberto Eco and Russian scientist Vyacheslav Ivanov, in collaboration with his Georgian colleague Teymuraz Gamkrelidze, did not find it easy to carry out special research on this topic (Eco 1997; Gamkrelidze, Ivanov 1984; Bomherd 1984).

Of course, it is necessary to gain the value of such research, to pay respect to scholars who have devoted themselves to this field, but for the development of the science of linguistics, it is necessary to know the language in which Adam and Eve communicated in the Garden of Eram, or to find a language that is acceptable to all mankind (this language is nothing but an artificial one). "How does Leeson seek to mature?" rather than spending time and ingenuity to create something; "What is linguistic maturity and what form does it take?"; "Are the stages of the development of the language system the stages of the formation of linguistic maturity?"; "Is maturity specific to each national language or does it have to be a common language?"; "Is the development of the national literary language an example of maturity?" We are sure that the answer to such questions is more effective.

It is known that language is a gift given only to man. Therefore, the study of linguistic phenomena is fundamentally different from the study of other social phenomena. According to the modern philosophical direction, synergetics, all natural and social phenomena have a systematic structure and self-organization. It has long been recognized that language is a systematic phenomenon, the attention of linguists is focused on a number of issues such as how this system is organized, what types of units are in its structure, the interaction of these units, the general system and its place in the hierarchical structure of the structures formed on the basis of these relations. However, the complete scientific knowledge of the object is not only limited to the structural analysis of the system, but it is natural to be interested in how this system "works" (or is used). The peculiarity of the language system is its "duality", that is, it consists of two

systems. In fact, linguistic activity consists of two main parts: the pronunciation of language units and the meaning and content expressed through them.

The French linguist A. Martine, in his treatise "Basics of General Linguistics", describes the language as a "double pronunciation (pronounced twice)" phenomenon ("Martinet 1964; Martine 1963"), and assumes that this phenomenon consists of sound pronunciation and meaning expression. Therefore, any research on the language system should take into account its "duality", two-system nature. The science of linguistics follows the same path in its development stages. In research areas such as system-structural, descriptive, comparative-typological, developed over the centuries, the main attention was paid to the performance of tasks such as separating one or another unit, determining their relations in the spheres of expression and meaning, distinguishing descriptive signs and thus dividing them into classification groups. As a result, it was thought that having knowledge about the plans of expression and meaning allows to find answers to the questions about the "working" of the language or how the thinking ability of a person is activated during the use of this language.

Also, as a result of the search for units of exactly the same structure, content and content in different language systems, users of all languages follow the same rules, and this rule is not different from each other.

Of course, as we begin to learn more and more about the nature of language, its essence in human life, which is only a human phenomenon, new questions arise, and the need to re-examine the previous questions and the answers to them (if necessary, deny some of them) grows. Linguistics is an empirical science, theoretical ideas in it are constantly formed based on the analysis of accumulated evidence (even scientific hypotheses require constant proof). Therefore, it is inevitable that the interest of linguists in studying the main structural units of the language (phoneme, morpheme, word, sentence, etc.) will not fade away. But in order to fully understand the basic nature of language, it is necessary to study the organizational parts of human linguistic activity, its internal phenomena, in addition to external phenomena.

The 19th century German linguist Wilhelm von Humboldt, who was not satisfied with the results of the analysis of the external forms of the units of the language system, used the concept of "inner (inner) form of the language" (innere Sprach form): "It is the inner and fully intellectual aspect of the language, and it is this aspect that constitutes the language" (Humboldt 1984: 100). In later periods, efforts were made to consider the concept of "the inner form of the language" as a concept related to logic, as it reflects the "only intellectual" aspect of the language, and in this regard to push it out of the scope of linguistics (for example, in England - O. Funke, in Germany

H. Steinthal, B. Wundt, G. Shpit in Russia), this concept in many cases serves as the main idea of raising the scientific knowledge of the language to a new level. It should be so, because the "intellectual part" of the language is not a logical or psychological category, but the same part that provides opportunities to use the language, that is, "linguistic creativity uses sound forms" and has the characteristic of expressing all new concepts (Humboldt 1984: 100).

Another of the ideas that motivated the rise of the science of linguistics to a new level appeared at the beginning of the 20th century. Ferdinand de Saussure, one of the linguists who searched for the "objective methods" of scientific clarification of the language system, put forward the idea that language should be viewed as a system of signs. Saussure, the founder of linguistic systemology, stated that its main principles are related to distinguishing between language and speech phenomena, synchronic and diachronic methods of analysis, and taking into account the arbitrariness of the linguistic sign.

There is no need to emphasize how important the *dichotomy of language* and speech was for the development of 20th century linguistics. This contradiction discovered by Saussure (despite the fact that there are enough critical opinions expressed about it) has been attracting the attention of scientists (not only linguists) who are working in different directions in all regions of the world. It is known that in his lectures, Saussure described the pair of language and speech in the contrast of the following characteristics: *sociality - individuality, abstraction - precision, passivity - activity, mental - physical, possibility (hidden) - realization, virtual - actuality*, etc.

The most criticized of these are sociality-personality and passivity-activity contrasts. If we follow the opinion expressed by E. Koseriu at the time, the distinction between language and speech is perfect (because language and speech are not exactly the same thing), but Saussure's view of this distinction as having an opposite nature and thus "cutting off" language from speech is controversial (Koseriu 1963: 151).

How can language and speech be contrasted, one cut off from the other? No matter how much Saussure himself tried to emphasize that language and speech are "completely separate things", he had no choice but to recognize the interdependence of these two phenomena: "both of these subjects are closely related and require each other: speech is intelligible and therefore effective language must exist in order to exist; and speech is necessary for the formation of language, its composition" (Saussure 1977: 57).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research conducted by Saussure scholars in the following years testifies to the need to interpret the relationship between language and speech not as an antagonistic relationship, but

as a phenomenon requiring interdependence. Professor Rudolph Engler of the University of Bern, a student of the famous Saussure scholar R. Gödel, is preparing a four-volume critical text of the "General Linguistics Course" for publication, based on a comparison of the texts of all the notebooks written by the students of this course (Saussure 1967:74) in order to understand Saussure's thoughts about language and speech logically.

As mentioned above, giving language the qualities of "social and passive" and speech "individual and active" has been severely criticized by many. But "If we look more closely at the direction of Saussure's thought," writes R. Engler, "we will be forced to completely change the description and definition; for our definition of language as a passive phenomenon (as opposed to the activity of speech) is indeed a definition that cannot be grasped at all. If we recognize that the active force of linguistic activity moves language, activates it, the given definition takes on a different tone" (Engler 1998: XVI).

In some cases, the reason for the incorrect description of the relationship between language and speech phenomena is associated with inaccuracies in the interpretation of the concepts of *langage – langue – parole* in the French language. It is known that Saussure himself felt the difficulties in the choice and definition of the terms in this trio. Having shown the extent to which the alternatives of French terms in German and Latin languages do not correspond in content, the scientist concludes that "it is impossible to find a single word that fully corresponds to any of the above concepts, and therefore it is useless to define these words" (Saussure 1977: 52).

This warning of Saussure should have prompted his followers and translators to be careful. But unfortunately, different versions appeared in the translations. For example, the alternative in the German language took the form of *langue - Sprache, langage - Rede* (Menschliche Rede), *parole - das Sprechen*, and in English, terms such as *langage - speech* (human speech), *langue - language, parole - speaking* came into use. Of the concepts in this line, the one that causes the most misunderstandings are *langage*.

In almost all cases, this concept has been interpreted in connection with human speech ability. Compare: The German *Rede* (Menschliche Rede) and the English *speech* (human speech) variants included the concept of "speech (human speech)". Similarly, the editors of the Russian translation of the 1933 edition of "Kurs" R.O. Shor and D.N. Vvedensky believe that *langage* corresponds to the concept of "rechevaya deyatelnost". The editor of the Russian edition of "Kurs" in 1977, A.A. Kholodovich, noted that *langage* means the concept of "generalization, integrity of linguistic phenomena", but preferred to keep the translation "rechevaya deyatelnost"

(Saussure 1977: 23).

Such inattention to the terms caused to look at the concept of language in a narrow sense, i.e. in the scope of actions, a set of features, activities related to speech performance.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

In our opinion, the phrase "speech activity" ("rehevaya deyatel'nost'") does not fully reflect the meaning of the concept of language used by Saussure, because language refers to the ability and characteristic of a community (not an individual). Only the manifestation of this ability in the activity of an individual can be considered as "speech" and "speech ability". In fact, it is not surprising that Saussure used the concept of language to reflect the relationship between language and speech, to emphasize that they constitute a dialectical whole by nature, that one cannot exist without the other. After all, we know that in one of his lectures at the University of Geneva in November 1891, the scientist stressed the need to look at language and language phenomena as a whole: "Any attempt to study linguistic activity without studying the circumstances of its manifestation (occurrence) is ineffective; Also, the effort to learn separate languages is an exercise that does not have any serious significance and real scientific basis if it is forgotten that these languages follow certain principles and rules that are generalized within the framework of the concept of linguistic activity" (Saussure 1990:37).

As the author wishes, the concept of language should fully and completely reflect the linguistic reality. Therefore, I believe that this concept should be understood in the context of human linguistic activity. The editors of recent Russian translations of Saussure's legacy also prefer to replace the term language with the phrase «языковая деятельность» (Saussure 1990; Saussure 1998).

Saussure's followers not only continue his teaching, but also try to enrich it with new ideas and clarify the interpretation of these ideas. Therefore, G. Guillaume (1883-1960), a scientist who considered himself a direct follower of Saussure, the founder of the theory of psychosystematics, said that linguistic activity is not a simple result sum of "language + speech", but a dynamic combination. approved to be considered as a joint (common) existence. That is why he prefers to express the commonality of these parts through the concept of "integral" rather than "summary" (Guillaume 1992: 166; Skrelina 1980:9):

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that the critics of Chomsky's theory felt the need to expand the concept of "linguistic ability" and favored the concept of "communicative competence". In my opinion, these two concepts do not negate each other, because in order to have communicative

ability, it is necessary to have linguistic knowledge and the ability to use the creative possibilities of language. Similarly, linguistic ability itself is necessary for communicative cooperation; its formation is a requirement of communicative need. This need, in turn, is born in social conditions, in the process of cooperative activity of individuals. Therefore, it was inevitable that the science of language should move towards communication features such as human relations and the role of language in the course of such relations, the manifestation of creative features of language in the process of performing this role. The teachings of dozens of scientists, such as Humboldt, Saussure, Chomsky, Baudouin de Courtenay, Shcherba, caused the emergence of a new scientific-paradigm-communicative-pragmatic analysis direction in the field of linguistics and serves as a theoretical base for this direction.

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